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Development of a digital model of a stationary hydrogen storage tank based on room temperature (TiFe) hydride

Helmholtz-Zentrum
hereon

Development of a digital model of a stationary hydrogen storage tank based on room temperature (TiFe) hydride

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Abstract

In this work, the digital twin of an existing solid-state hydrogen storage tank is developed by applying the finite elements method (FEM). The hydrogen storage tank contains a pelletized room temperature alloy (TiFeMn) as hydride forming material. To build the digital twin, the kinetic, thermodynamic, and intrinsic relationships are determined using experimental and mathematical methods to mimic the behavior of the real tank. Theoretical and experimental approaches allow comparing the obtained model with the experimental results of the real tank. Moreover, the hydride bed's operative conditions and geometrical characteristics are optimized to improve the performance of the hydrogen storage device. As a result, it is found that the simulative results mimic the behavior of the real tank quite well. In the case of the parameters optimization, it is found that a variation of the operating pressure and the coolant temperature had a predominantly linear trend, but limitations with respect to the pressure could be worked out for the desorption. The variation of the coolant velocity is highly efficacious up to 2 m/s. However, a further increase of the coolant velocity does not improve the tank's performance notably. The geometry optimization is carried out by varying the number of pelletized hydride material keeping the total mass of material constant. It is found that increasing the number of pellets has a positive effect on the reaction process, but this does not show a proportional trend. The development of the digital model and the optimization analyses result in a deeper understanding of transport phenomena at a large scale, identifying the optimal operative conditions for the current design and proposing improvements to the current design.

Zusammenfassung

In dieser Arbeit wird der digitale Zwilling eines bestehenden Festkörper-Wasserstoffspeichers durch Anwendung der Finite-Elemente-Methode (FEM) entwickelt. Der Wasserstoffspeicher enthält eine pelletierte Raumtemperaturlegierung (TiFeMn) als hydridbildendes Material. Zum Aufbau des digitalen Zwillings werden die kinetischen, thermodynamischen und intrinsischen Beziehungen mit experimentellen und mathematischen Methoden bestimmt, um das Verhalten des realen Tanks nachzuahmen. Theoretische und experimentelle Ansätze ermöglichen den Vergleich des erhaltenen Modells mit den experimentellen Ergebnissen des realen Tanks. Darüber hinaus werden die Betriebsbedingungen und geometrischen Eigenschaften des Hydrids optimiert, um die Leistung des Wasserstoffspeichers zu verbessern. Als Ergebnis wird festgestellt, dass die simulativen Ergebnisse das Verhalten des realen Tanks gut nachahmen. Bei der Parameteroptimierung zeigt sich, dass eine Variation des Betriebsdrucks und der Kühlmitteltemperatur einen überwiegend linearen Verlauf hat, für die Desorption konnten jedoch Einschränkungen bezüglich des Drucks herausgearbeitet werden. Die Variation der Kühlmittelgeschwindigkeit ist bis zu 2 m/s hochwirksam. Eine weitere Erhöhung der Kühlmittelgeschwindigkeit führt jedoch nicht zu einer nennenswerten Verbesserung der

Tankleistung. Die Geometrieoptimierung wird durch Variation der Anzahl der pelletierten Hydrid-Materialien durchgeführt, wobei die Gesamtmasse des Materials konstant gehalten wird. Es wird festgestellt, dass die Erhöhung der Anzahl der Pellets einen positiven Effekt auf den Reaktionsprozess hat, dieser jedoch keinen proportionalen Trend aufweist. Die Entwicklung des digitalen Modells und die Optimierungsanalysen führen zu einem tieferen Verständnis der Transportphänomene in großem Maßstab, zur Identifizierung der optimalen Betriebsbedingungen und zu Verbesserungsvorschlägen für das aktuelle Design.

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Nomenclature

Arabic characters	Significance	Unit
c	Specific Heat Capacity	J/kg K
C _f	Shape Factor	-
E _a	Activation Energy	J/mol
A	Frequency Factor	1/s
m	Mass	kg
M	Molar Mass	kg/mol
p	Pressure	bar
q	Heat Flux	W
R	Universal Gas Constant	J/mol K
t	Time	s
T	Temperature	°C
v	Velocity	m/s
k _{eff}	Effective Thermal Conductivity	W/m K
h	Convective Heat Transfer Coefficient	W/m ² K
H	Enthalpy	J/mol
s	Entropy	J/mol K
L	Solubility	mol/l
K	Permeability	m ²

Greek characters	Significance	Unit
α	Hydrogen Fraction	-
ρ	Density	kg/m ³
ϕ	Porosity	-
μ	Dynamic Viscosity	Kg/m s
ν	Kinematic Viscosity	m ² /s

Abbreviation	Significance
MH	Metal hydride
eff	Effective
rad	Radiation
p	Pressure
p _{eq}	Equilibrium Pressure
Abs	Absorption

Des	Desorption
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
PCI	Pressure Concentration Isotherm
Re	Reynolds number
Pr	Prandtl number
Nu	Nußelt number
FEM	Finite Element Method

Element symbol	Chemical element
Fe	Iron
H	Hydrogen
H ₂	Molecular hydrogen
Mn	Manganese

1 Introduction

As this decade begins, major political, economic, and social efforts are being made to minimize anthropogenic carbon emissions. In many areas, the goal of the Paris Agreement is being attempted to be undercut. Countries are setting themselves the global goal of limiting global warming to "well below" two degrees Celsius compared to the pre-industrial era, with efforts to limit it to 1.5 °C. Even large CO_2 emitters such as China have set themselves the goal of asserting economic interests and protecting the climate. This is important because a large part of the products is produced there, which are essential for the changeover to renewable energies in Europe. The ecological harmonization time of a solar cell produced by renewable energies is significantly lower than a solar cell produced by fossil energies.

In order to achieve the goals of the Paris climate agreement or even higher goals, a stringent transformation of energy in all areas is necessary.

We need efficient energy storage for a successful energy transition away from fossil fuels and toward renewable energy sources. Renewable energies are available in almost unlimited quantities, but not in a base load-capable state, as is the case with a coal-fired or nuclear power plant. In addition to the further expansion of renewable energies and the transport of energy to areas with fewer opportunities to supply renewable energies, the critical factor for the successful energy transition is the efficient storage of electricity from renewable energies. Only if this is achieved will it be possible to ensure the base-load operation and dispense with fossil and nuclear power plants in the long term. Of course, hydroelectric power plants, biomass power plants and geothermal power plants are also available for a small part of the base-load. However, this is highly regionally dependent and Germany, for example, has already expanded a large part of its capacity.

There are many possibilities for storing surplus energy when large amounts of renewable energy can be produced, for example, during the day via photovoltaics or with the wind. However, the requirements are high. This is because a great deal of energy has to be stored in the short term, and this energy has to be available quickly, or it has to be storable for several weeks. In principle, electrical energy can only be stored if it is converted into another form. This can be, for example, conversion into kinetic or potential energy, conversion into chemical energy in the form of potential or concentration differences, or conversion of the aggregate state.

A promising process of conversion of electrical energy into chemically bound energy is the electrolysis of hydrogen. Hydrogen is an effective energy vector and can be used in a variety of ways. Hydrogen can be converted electrochemically into electrical power in a fuel cell, but

it can also be converted thermochemically into energy, for example, in hydrogen combustions engines in cars.

Various options can be considered for the storage of hydrogen. On the one hand, hydrogen can be stored under high pressure or cryogenic temperatures. Until now, conventional and mass production storage of hydrogen under high pressure has been carried out in complex pressure vessels. This is already well established for mobile applications due to its rapid availability. Due to the high pressure of the hydrogen, a downstream consumer, such as a fuel cell, can be fed directly. Storing hydrogen at pressures of up to 700 bar requires complex and cost-intensive tank systems.

Furthermore, the supply of hydrogen at filling stations is only possible using large compressors. Compression and long-term provision of this form of storage require a high level of energy. The storage of hydrogen in liquid form is a possibility for storage in stationary applications. For this purpose, the hydrogen is strongly cooled down until it reaches a temperature of about 21.2 K [9]. With this form of storage, a volume-related energy density of about $70 \frac{\text{kg H}_2}{\text{m}^3}$ can be achieved [8]. Thus, a great deal of energy must be expended to reach the target temperature. Due to heat losses, the so-called "boil-off" effect, up to 0.4 % of the stored hydrogen is released to the environment every day. The high amounts of energy for liquefaction and the daily loss make the storage process very expensive and unprofitable [9].

On the other hand, it is also possible to store hydrogen efficiently by forming metal hydrides at moderate pressures and room temperature. The hydrogen storage in MH was technically developed for the first time in the 1960s [9]. They were further developed in the 1970s due to the oil crisis in 1975 when alternative energy sources were sought. Due to the comparatively low volumetric energy density of MH to date, a mobile application was out of the question for the automotive industry because of the resulting higher weight. All hydrogen storage options consider the fact that hydrogen has a relatively high gravimetric energy density combined with a low volumetric energy density. The low volumetric energy density of gaseous hydrogen at ambient temperature leads to challenges in transporting and storing hydrogen.

In MH storage systems, hydrogen reacts with solid materials and forms a new phase: the hydride phase. This phase formation can already be achieved at moderate pressures and temperatures. These materials are handled in a powder form and absorb hydrogen at temperatures between -80 °C and 50 °C and pressures between 10 bar and 30 bar [3]. This temperature and pressure range is ideal for operation with a fuel cell. During the exothermic absorption of the hydrogen in the MH, the heat can be partly used for the fuel cell. During the endothermic desorption process, the required heat is provided by the waste heat of the fuel cell. Moreover, the reversible desorption reaction can be performed even under 1 bar of

pressure. Due to the atomic incorporation of hydrogen in the metal lattice, storage in metal hydrides entails a high volumetric density of about $100 \frac{\text{kg H}_2}{\text{m}^3}$ for the TiFe alloy [3].

Due to the above-mentioned favorable properties of storing hydrogen as a metal hydride and the clear need for a suitable storage system for the energy transition, the continuous and further development of hydride forming alloys and tank development is of great importance. Since an actual test setup is associated with enormous costs, investigations on different tank systems and hydride forming alloys through suitable computer simulation methods such as FEM (Finite Element Method) are required. Applying FEM, it is possible to design a MH-storage system based on the hydrogenation-dehydrogenation kinetic, thermodynamic behavior and transport phenomena such as heat, mass, and momentum. FEM offers flexibility in the variation of parameters, associated with high costs in a scale-up experimental set up. Nevertheless, validation of the developed model through experiments in a build experimental set up is always required at the end of a process.

1.1 Project „HyCARE“

In the frame of this master thesis, the developed FEM model pursues to mimic the behavior and investigate the possible improvements to the design of a scaled-up experimental MH-storage system based on pelletized TiFeMn hydride forming alloy.

The goal of the European project "Hydrogen Carrier for Renewable Energy Storage" (HyCARE) has been to develop and use the largest civilian-use MH storage tank with a storage capacity of up to 50 kg of hydrogen. The tank was planned to be coupled with a 20 kW PEM electrolyzer and a 10 kW PEM fuel cell. Therefore, the electrolyzer provides the hydrogen to be stored in the MH-system, and the hydrogen is supplied to the fuel cell when it is required. The system will be installed and commissioned at the end of the research project at the "ENGIE Lab Crigen" in France [12].

Due to the connected electrolyzer and fuel cell, only room temperature hydrides are used for the storage. These exhibit rapid charging and discharging. TiFeMn alloys, which can also be produced on an industrial scale, are used as room temperature hydride.

2 Theoretical Background

In this chapter, the theoretical principles and state of the art on metal hydride storage are presented. The physical fundamentals of the absorption and desorption of hydrogen in metal hydrides is also discussed. Furthermore, an insight into the finite element methods is given, and the fundamental differential equations which are necessary for the simulation are introduced.

2.1 Hydrogen storage in metal hydrides

As early as the 1960s and 1970s, a great deal of research was devoted to the goal of developing a safe and compact hydrogen storage system based on metal-hydrogen reactions. It was found that a large number of metallic alloys can chemically and reversibly store hydrogen by forming metal hydrides [9]. Since the absorption of hydrogen is an exothermic process, i.e. heat is released during the storage of hydrogen in the metal hydride, an MH store can also be defined as a heat store.

As shown in equation (2.1) for the absorption of hydrogen in a metal alloy, a quantity of metal alloy multiplied by factor “ y ” plus a quantity of hydrogen multiplied by factor “ x ” is converted into a metal hydride by releasing the reaction enthalpy. The metal hydride then has the composition of “ y ” parts metal alloy and “ x ” parts hydrogen [25; 10].

As can be seen from this equation, a quantity of heat must be dissipated to load the alloy with hydrogen, while heat must be supplied to remove the hydrogen, i.e. to decompose the hydride.

As can be seen in figure 1, in the first step of the absorption process, the gaseous hydrogen meets the metal alloy in molecular form. In the second step, the physisorption, the molecular hydrogen is adsorptively bound to the substrate through van der Waals forces. During chemisorption, the molecular hydrogen separates into individual hydrogen atoms [2]. The strong bonding of the hydrogen molecule to the metal alloy causes the intramolecular bonding in the adsorbed molecules to dissociate. The dissociated hydrogen now has the opportunity to diffuse into the metal lattice. Thus, the α -phase is formed from a solid solution of hydrogen in the metal matrix. Before a pure β -phase is formed, in which the hydrogen is completely bound in the metal hydride species, a two-phase region is formed in which the α -phase and the β -phase coexist.

Figure 1: Hydrogenation process [14]

To investigate the formation of metal hydrides under equilibrium conditions, concentration-pressure isotherms (PCI) are determined experimentally (Figure 2). PCI curves allow determining several relevant characteristics of the metal hydrogen system. These isotherms represent the formation process of the hydride phase under equilibrium conditions. Three main steps can describe such a process.

After the hydrogen molecules (H_2) are dissociated into hydrogen atoms (H), they enter the metal alloy and form a solid solution. According to the Sieverts law, the solubility (L_{H_2}) is a function of the pressure (p_{H_2}) as described in equation (2.2).

$$L_{H_2} \sim \sqrt{p_{H_2}} \quad (2.2)$$

This process occurs until the saturation concentration is reached (α -phase) as shown in figure 2. In this solubility range, there are 2 components (C), namely metal and hydrogen, and 2 phases (P), a gaseous phase of hydrogen and a solid phase of metal. Applying Gibb's phase rule (2.3), the degrees of freedom can be determined as:

$$C - P + 2 = F \quad (2.3)$$

In this case, according to Gibbs' phase rule, the system possesses two degrees of freedom the pressure and the temperature.

After the saturation concentration is reached, the concentration continues increasing and the hydride phase is formed under isobaric conditions (β -phase), as can be seen in figure 2 for the plateau region. Applying the Gibbs phase rule, it is possible to determine the degrees of freedom dependent on the process control. Since the metal hydride phase is being formed in this range, there are two fixed phases, which reduces the degrees of freedom to one. At a constant temperature, the degree of freedom falls to zero, and therefore the formation of the metal hydride takes place under constant pressure.

According to Sieverts' law, at the end of the plateau, the pressure increases quadratically, and hydrogen is dissolved in the hydride phase. The length of the plateau is thus an approximate measurement of the usable storage capacity of a material at a given temperature.

In the case of absorption, the equilibrium is shifted to the side of the hydride by increasing the hydrogen concentration. In addition to the increase in concentration, the equilibrium position can also be changed by the thermodynamic boundary conditions. The relationship of the reaction equilibrium and the thermodynamic boundary conditions is expressed by the van't-Hoff isotherm, which is seen in figure 2. The plateau pressure can be expressed for a limited temperature range by equation (2.4).

$$\ln\left(\frac{p_{H_2}}{p_0}\right) = \frac{\Delta H}{R \cdot T} - \frac{\Delta S}{R} \quad (2.4)$$

Here, p_{H_2} represents the equilibrium pressure of the system in the plateau region, p_0 is the reference pressure (1 bar), R is the universal gas constant, ΔH describes the enthalpy of reaction and, ΔS the entropy of binding. As seen in equation (2.4), the equilibrium pressure depends on the temperature T . The ΔH indicates the strength of the metal-hydrogen bond, and the ΔS denotes the gas-solid entropy changes of hydrogen.

The van't Hoff equation can be used to calculate the enthalpy and entropy of reaction from the PCI curves as shown in figure 2, right. The enthalpy is obtained from the slope of the van't Hoff function and the entropy from the intercept to the origin in the ordinate axis. Furthermore, it is possible to calculate the temperature level under hydrogen release pressure of 1 bar,

which is decisive for technical use to evaluate the range of applications of the studied forming hydride material, i.e., from equation (2.4), $T = \frac{\Delta H}{\Delta S}$ [18].

Figure 2: Schematic concentration-pressure isotherms for different temperatures (left) and van't Hoff isotherm determined from plateau pressures (right).

Another essential characteristic of the hydride formation/decomposition is the kinetic behavior. The reaction rate depends on three factors, i.e. temperature, pressure, and morphological changes of the material. First, the temperature dependence ($K(T)$) described by the Arrhenius expression, as expressed in equation (2.5).

$$K(T) = A \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right) \quad (2.5)$$

Where A is the pre-exponential factor (probability of encounter), E_a is the activation energy (energy required to initiate the reaction), R is the universal gas constant, and T the temperature in absolute units.

Second, the functionality of the pressure ($F(P_{op}, P_{eq})$), which describes the relationship between the operative pressure (P_{op}) and the equilibrium pressure (P_{eq}), and describes the driving force for the reaction. Different types of equations describe the $F(P)$, which depends on the kind of material and the kinetic conditions [19].

Both functionalities, $K(T)$ and $F(P)$ describe the kinetic constant as seen in equation (2.6).

$$k(T, p) = A \text{EXP} \left(-\frac{E\alpha}{RT} \right) F(p, p_{eq}) \quad (2.6)$$

Finally, the reaction rate still depends on the morphological changes of the material related to the rate-limiting step, described by the function $G(\alpha)$, where α describes the fraction of hydrogen absorbed or desorbed during the process. This functionality, $G(\alpha)$, can be described by applying gas-solid models, which describe the rate-limiting step: the nucleation and the growth of hydride seeds, diffusion processes through hydride layer, surface processes, and contractive nuclei processes [27]. Considering $K(T)$, $(F(P_{op}, P_{eq}))$ and $G(\alpha)$, the reaction rate can be expressed applying the separable variables equation as describes in the equation (2.7).

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = k(T, P)G(\alpha) \quad (2.7)$$

2.2 Finite element methods

The finite element method (FEM) is a general numerical procedure applied to various physical problems. FEM is based on the numerical solution of a complex system of differential equations. It has its origin in structural analysis. A mathematical description of the method was already given in 1943 [21]. Several processes in science and technology are described through partial differential equations of first and second order. First-order differential equations contain a derivative of the independent variable. In the case of derivatives with respect to time, these often represent an energy store [21]. As already described, there is an economic need for suitable modeling of real problems since experimental setups can sometimes be very costly. At the beginning of the modeling process, it is necessary to simplify the real problem and convert it into a mathematical model. The mathematical model is then generally based on partial differential equations that physically describe the real problem. Now the solution of these partial differential equations is required, which is sometimes not always possible to solve with an exact solution. However, for most applications, approximated results are sufficient given the high complexity of the real problems. Before the partial differential equations can be solved, they have to be discretized in a suitable way. Discretization is the division of the computational domain into sub-domains with an appropriate element type. Then the component (i.e., the calculation area) is divided into elements (sub-domains): the "finite elements". This is usually

specific scheme, which is described below and can be seen in figure 4. At the beginning of the modeling, the desired geometry level must be selected. This starts at 0D and goes through 1D and 1D axisymmetric to 2D and 2D axisymmetric to a 3D model. A model simplified in the geometry level saves enormous amounts of computing power. Once the model is created, it is possible to apply the desired physical effects to the different areas. In addition, different materials can be selected and assigned to areas to consider the different material behavior in the simulation. By selecting appropriate initial and boundary conditions, the model becomes more realistic, and this is also mandatory for the numerical solution. The generation of a mesh adapted to the geometry is also mandatory. The last step is to select whether the study should be carried stationary or time-dependent. If the study was successful and converged after a certain amount of internal and external iteration of the coupled partial differential equations, there is the possibility to evaluate the results comprehensively. Physics-dependent parameters as well as specially created parameters and variables can be visualized and analyzed.

Despite the extensive content of this software package, the essential task of the software is to compile the partial differential equations and solve them together. Each problem to be solve presents its physio-chemical background. In this particular case, the physio-chemical description of the hydrogen absorption and desorption process in metal hydrides are added from experimental gathered data and the knowledge in the subject of the research group. The software solves the partial differential equations for the change of concentration, temperature, or transport properties, based on the provided physio-chemical background of the investigated phenomena.

Figure 4: COMSOL Workflow

2.3 Design of solid-state hydrogen storage tanks: Numerical and technical

2.3.1 Numerical design

To create a numerical model of a metal hydride tank, several fundamental physical phenomena must be considered. 1) The chemical reaction during absorption and desorption, which describes the reaction rate, i.e., the change in concentration over time. 2) The transfer of heat generated or required during the reaction and 3) The hydrogen transport through the metal hydride and the shell of the tank.

Mass balance

The change of hydrogen concentration in a metal hydride can be described by Fick's law (2.8).

$$\frac{\partial c_i}{\partial t} + \nabla J_i + u \nabla c_i = R_i \quad (2.8)$$

This equation is sufficient for modeling the diffusion and convective transport of chemical species and addresses the conservation of mass for one or more species i . In this case ∇J_i describes the mass transport due to molecular diffusion. J_i is the mass diffusive flux vector and depends on the concentration gradient ∇c and the diffusion coefficient D_i as described in equation (2.9).

$$J_i = -D \nabla c \quad (2.9)$$

In the case of the proposed modeling, the change of concentration only depends on the reaction kinetics (R_i) since the included intrinsic kinetic describe the rate-limiting step, which involves the transport phenomena of species related to the change of concentrations.

Heat transfer

Heat transfer takes place via three different mechanisms: conduction, convection, and radiation. In this work, two main mechanisms are considered, the conduction and the convection mechanism. The mathematically and physically most straightforward transfer of

heat from one body to another can be described by heat conduction. According to the second law of thermodynamics, heat always flows from a higher temperature level to a lower temperature level. The Fourier law describes the heat conduction of particles and movements of electrons within a body. In a homogeneous and isotropic body, the heat transfer by conduction can be described with the following partial differential equation (2.10).

$$\frac{\partial T(r, t)}{\partial t} = a(T) \cdot \Delta T(r, t) \quad (2.10)$$

Here, $a(T)$ describes a temperature-dependent coefficient for the heat conductivity in $\frac{W}{m \cdot K}$.

Other forms of heat transfer include heat convection, in which heat is transferred by particle mass transport, such as the flow of fluid. This particle transport can, for example, be caused by the fact that a density difference arises due to the heating and rising air on the body surface carries heat with it. Thermal radiation describes the third form of heat transfer. For this form of heat transfer, no particles are needed, and the bodies do not have to touch each other. Heat radiation, therefore, also works in a vacuum. The radiation is transmitted with the help of electromagnetic waves, following the Stefan-Boltzmann law.

Transport of hydrogen

The transport of hydrogen through the metal hydride is described by Darcy's law. The Darcy law is used for porous media and low flow rates. The driving force is the pressure difference. In real metal hydride storage tanks, however, space is left between the metal hydride and the tank shell for the expansion of the metal hydride during absorption. For a holistic simulation, either Darcy's law should be combined with the Navier-Stokes equation and boundary conditions. For this purpose, the Darcy's law for the porous medium and the Navier-Stokes equation for the free flow are solved separately and combined with suitable boundary conditions. Another possibility to simulate a free flow and a flow through a porous medium can be achieved with the Brinkman equation. This is also a mixture of the Darcy's law and the Navier-Stokes equation, but they are simulated simultaneously, and the coupling is done via boundary conditions.

The term "porous media" refers to materials that consist of a solid matrix with a connected void space [6].

In this subchapter, the modeling for calculating fluxes in porous and free areas through different model approaches are briefly discussed.

Navier-Stokes Equation

The Navier-Stokes equations allow a mathematical model for the simulation of flows of linearly viscous Newtonian fluids. They extend the Euler equations by terms for the consideration of the viscosity. Fundamental for the Navier-Stokes equations is the conservation of momentum. However, the conservation of mass also plays a central role in calculating compressible flows. With the inclusion of energy conservation, the well-known set of non-linear partial differential equations of second order arises. The exact derivation of the fundamental equations mentioned will not be further considered here since it is out of the scope of this work. It is of interest that the derivation of the basic equations is done in principle by different methods, but two different representations are usually used.

On the one hand, the Lagrange representation can be used. Here, the motion is described by specifying the coordinates of individual fluid particles as a function of time. On the other hand, the Eulerian representation describes the flow with field quantities. These field quantities are physical properties of the space [26]. Using these representations, the conservation equations for mass, momentum, and energy for a compressible fluid can be summarized as Navier-Stokes equations (2.11).

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho u_i)}{\partial x_i} &= 0 & I. \\
 \frac{\partial(\rho u_j)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho u_i u_j)}{\partial x_i} &= -\frac{\partial p}{\partial x_j} - \frac{\partial \tau_{ij}}{\partial x_i} + \rho g_j & II. \\
 cv \left[\frac{\partial(\rho T)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho u_i T)}{\partial x_i} \right] &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[\lambda \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_i} \right] - p \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_i} - \tau_{ij} \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} & III. \\
 \tau_{ij} &= -\mu \left[\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right] + \frac{2}{3} \mu \delta_{ij} \frac{\partial u_k}{\partial x_k} & IV.
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.11}$$

In this system of equations, the term I. describes the conservation of mass. Term II. represents the conservation of momentum and term III. the conservation of energy. Term IV, the molecular momentum transport, gives rise to the Navier-Stokes system of equations. A further breakdown of the indices can be found in the nomenclature.

This system of equations can be further simplified for various applications and special cases, such as for an incompressible Newtonian fluid. Also, the equation system can be transformed into a dimensionless form. This could be necessary for different similarity analyses.

Darcy's Law

The work "Les Fontaines publiques de la ville de Dijon" by French engineer Henry Darcy, published in 1856, describes the construction of Dijon's water supply system. In the appendix of his work, he describes his experiments with water flowing through sand and derives an empirical law [16]. This simplification of the Navier-Stokes equation, known as Darcy's law, plays an essential role in petroleum engineering, civil engineering, chemical engineering and soil science, and other sciences. To determine his law, the engineer used the apparatus shown in Figure 5. A vertical iron pipe with a diameter of 0.35 meters and a length of 3.5 meters was flanged at both ends. At the height of 0.2 meters, a horizontal grid was attached, on which loose sand was piled up at the height of about 1 meter. The water was let into the system through a pipe at the top and could be taken out again at the bottom of the system. The tapped water was drained into a measuring tank 1 meter square and 0.5 meter deep.

Figure 5: Fascimile of Darcy's illustration of his experimental apparatus [16]

The flow rate could be controlled with adjustable valves in the inlet and outlet. The pressure was measured above and below the sand layer. For each series, the system was charged with different sand and completely filled with water. By adjusting the inlet and outlet valves, the water was caused to flow down through the sand at a series of successively increasing rates. For each rate, a reading was taken at the pressure gauges and recorded as the pressure difference in meters of water above the sand bottom. From this series of measurements, Darcy was able to determine three key findings. First, the discharge rate Q is proportional to the pressure difference, which was determined via the difference in the height of a mercury column (2.12).

$$Q \propto \Delta h := h_a - h_b \quad (2.12)$$

Furthermore, the discharge rate Q is inversely proportional to the thickness L_s of the sand layer (2.13).

$$Q \propto \frac{1}{L_s} \quad (2.13)$$

Finally, the discharge rate Q is proportional to the cross-sectional area A of the cylinder (2.14).

$$Q \propto A \quad (2.14)$$

The equations (2.13) to (2.15) then result in the Darcy law as follows (2.15) :

$$Q = KA \frac{\Delta h}{L_s} \quad (2.15)$$

Where K is a hydrolytic constant describing the permeability of the material.

Darcy's Law has been found to behave similarly to Ohm's Law in the conduction of electricity and Fourier's Law in the conduction of heat concerning to permeability in porous media.

Brinkman Equation

Due to the absence of the viscous stress tensor in the model developed by Darcy, which consequently yields good approximations only for small values of k , the Dutch physicist H.C. Brinkmann developed his model, the so-called Brinkman equations, in 1949 [1]. As a solution for this problem, he recommended modifying the Darcy equation (2.15) to (2.16).

$$Q = KA \frac{\Delta h}{L_s} + \eta \Delta \vec{v} \quad (2.16)$$

Here the term $\eta \Delta \vec{v}$ describes the extension of the darcy law by the viscosity term from the Stokes equation.

The Brinkman equation thus forms the transition from slowly flowing flows in porous media according to Darcy to fast flows in non-porous media, described by the Navier-Stokes equations. The velocity field v in the Brinkman equation describes the actual velocity in the pore space.

In the case of a small k , i.e., $k \rightarrow 0$ represents (2.15), an approximation of the Darcy equations since the damping term dominates the viscous stress tensor. This is called as Darcy limit. For $k \rightarrow \infty$, approximates (2.11) the equation for momentum conservation and is therefore called the Stokes limit.

2.3.2 Technical design

The greatest challenge in the design of metal hydride-based hydrogen storage tanks lies in the rapid dissipation of heat during exothermic absorption and rapid provision of heat during endothermic desorption. This also offers the most significant optimization potential when it comes to faster loading and unloading times. However, it also influences the capacity of the tank as well as the gravimetric hydrogen storage density. There are several ways to ensure the heat transfer of a metal hydride storage tank. Internal pipes, which pass through the hydride bed with flanged heat conducting plates, are installed in both co-current and counter-current principles. Another possibility of internal pipes is, for example, the helical arrangement. As well as designs where the hydride material is in tubes and the cooling medium in the tank flows around them. These are three common examples of the possibility of heat exchange in metal hydride storage. Not to be neglected, however, is the material-dependent thermal conductivity.

Of course, different alloys have different thermal conductivities, but the consistency of the alloy also has a significant influence on the thermal conductivity. If the alloy is ground in powder form, the thermal conductivity is usually lower than if the same alloy is sintered. The incorporation of hydrogen during absorption also reduces the thermal conductivity of the hydride by further orders of magnitude. However, it is precisely then that the reaction enthalpy is released, and a large amount of heat must be dissipated. If this heat is not dissipated quickly enough, the absorption process comes to a standstill. By adding additives such as graphite or aluminum, the thermal conductivity can be increased, but the disadvantage is the increase in the mass of the metal hydride without ensuring a linear increase in capacity. Table 1 shows some values for the thermal conductivity of known alloys. Another effect that affects the thermal conductivity but also the mechanical load on the tank is the volumetric expansion of the metal hydride caused by the absorption. If the alloy is in pressed pellet form, the aim is to dimensionalize the shell and the pellets in such a way that the expansion caused by the absorption fills the cavity between the pellets and the tank shell. Therefore, it has a positive effect on the overall thermal conductivity of the metal hydride. However, this also creates mechanical stresses on the tank shell, which are the subject of other research work. If the alloy material is in pellet form, it is also important for the advanced design. Metal hydride storage tanks with pellet material must have a flange so that the tank can be opened and loaded with the pellets. This is much easier for tanks with powder material, because this can be inserted into the tank through a small opening. A large flange for filling with pellets leads to more complicated simulations due to the flange behavior.

Alloy	Hydrogen pressure (bar)	Thermal conductivity (W/mK)
<i>FeTi</i>	1	1.28
not activated	5.1	1.35
	20.4	1.61
	34	1.77
	25	3.048
<i>FeTiMn</i> Sinter		
<i>Mg₂NiH₄</i>	1	0.56
	5	0.61
	35	0.65
<i>H₂</i>	1	0.19

Table 1: Thermal conductivity of common alloys [9; 23],

2.4 Scope of the work

As described in the previous chapters, the storage of electricity from renewable energies to bridge peak load times and to bridge times with only little available of solar energy and wind energy is the bottleneck of the energy transition towards a CO₂ neutral society. Possible ways of storing electrical energy have been identified, and the storage of energy as an energy vector as hydrogen is an essential component. In this frame, the scope of this work is the storage of hydrogen in TiFeMn metal hydrides. TiFeMn is a room temperature hydride and is available for this work in sintered pellet form. The objective of the work is to develop and evaluate the digital model of a tank equipped with TiFeMn pellets. This tank is fundamentally based on the tank developed for the HyCARE project, and the data obtained *via* the FEM simulation can thus be compared with the experimental performance of the tank. Here we start with the generation of models in 2D and 2D-axisymmetric geometries to validate the kinetic model, thermodynamic description as well as the heat and mass transfer and the transport of hydrogen in the tank and in the pellet with lower computation costs as seen in Figure 6. After validation of these phenomena, all the inputs of the 2D models are transfer to a 3D model. In the 3D model, the challenge is to mimic the behavior of the experimental tank but keeping low computational costs. The meshing of the geometry then also plays a critical role. In addition, the pellet material is further investigated experimentally. Considering the real reaction kinetics, the activation energy and the pre-exponential factor are determined from existing experimental data on the material applying a quadratic approximation method. The effective thermal conductivity of the TiFeMn pellet is determined experimentally since thermal management plays a significant role in the tank design, and no data are available for this material.

Simulation approach combined with experimental work

Figure 6: Simulation strategy

3 Experimental and numerical method

In this chapter, the experimental and numerical methods for obtaining the results of this work are explained. The experimental set up for the determination of the effective thermal conductivity and the corresponding physical background are described. The simulation procedures for determining the kinetic parameters are also described. Furthermore, an overview of the different models, used for the FEM simulation is given.

Regarding the numerical methods, the assumptions and simplifications are introduced. Moreover, the initial and boundary conditions necessary for the partial differential equations calculation are presented. Finally, the equations necessary to describe the absorption and desorption kinetic and thermodynamic behaviors of hydrogen in metal hydrides are provided.

3.1 Experimental techniques

3.1.1 Effective thermal conductivity

The effective thermal conductivity of a porous medium considers the thermal conduction of the solid material and includes the influence of gaseous material in the porous medium. This leads to the conclusion that pure heat conduction and other heat transport phenomena have to be considered. Thus, in addition to conductive heat transport, a combined heat transport mechanism is created, which takes into account solid and gaseous heat conduction. Here, large cavities in the porous bed are characterized by the thermal conductivity of the gas. Then at higher temperatures, heat is also transferred *via* the hot surfaces by means of thermal radiation.

There are different approaches to determine the effective thermal conductivity. On the one hand, this can be determined mathematically. For this purpose, mathematical relationships are used which depend, for example, on the porosity φ and an empirically determined form factor c_f in equation (3.1).

$$B = c_f \left(\frac{1 - \varphi}{\varphi} \right)^{\frac{10}{9}} \quad (3.1)$$

With the equation (3.1), *Zehner* and *Schlünder* provide a model to calculate k_{eff} , which is seen in the equation (3.2) [7].

$$k_{bed} = (1 - \sqrt{1 - \varphi})\varphi[(\varphi - 1 + k_G^{-1})^{-1} + k_{rad}] + \sqrt{1 - \varphi}[\theta_{fl}k_s + (1 - \theta_{fl})k_c] \quad (3.2)$$

This then takes into account thermal conduction, conductive components, and thermal radiation.

In this work, the effective thermal conductivity was determined experimentally. This is done in accordance with the work of *Jepsen, Puszkiel, et alii.* in [11]. For this purpose, a sample was worked out of the pellet material intended for the tank (Figure 7, Figure 8).

Figure 7: Shaping the TiFeMn material for effective thermal conductivity measurements

Figure 7 also shows the raw pellet material. This is based on an TiFeMn alloy and contains additional adhesive compounds, since this material was not classically sintered with heat, but cold-pressed. For the real tank, this pellet is provided with holes for cooling. Figure 8 shows the two pellets machined out in more detail. Sample 1 has a cylindrical shape in the dimensions of the sample holder used. Sample 2 also has a fine slit on one of the faces of the cylinder.

This is to provide the possibility that the measuring tips of the thermocouples in the sample holder are enclosed by more sample material.

Figure 8: TiFeMn Samples for effective thermal conductivity measurements

As can be seen from the detailed images (Figure 8) of the samples, the material is highly porous and brittle, making preparation in the sample holder form difficult. This is also why previous experimental measurements with this material were mainly performed in powder form.

These prepared samples could thus be introduced into the sample holder. At the bottom of the sample holder, there are four thermocouples that record the temperature in different radial positions (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Position of the thermocouples in the measurement cell

The sample holder is sealed and subjected to several absorption and desorption processes at a constant pressure of 30 bar, which is the operative pressure of the tank, and at different temperatures around the operating point of the simulated tank. The temperatures inside the sample are determined *via* the four measured peak maxima and the hydrogen charge and discharge are determined *via* a pressure difference and the sample weight. For the further calculation, the amount of heat introduced, which results from the enthalpy of reaction $\Delta H \left[\frac{J}{mol} \right]$ and the amount of hydrogen introduced $rate_{H_2} \left[\frac{mol_{H_2}}{kg \cdot s} \right]$ (3.4), is necessary, as well as the density of the material.

After the absorption or desorption is finished, the temperature difference between the four thermocouples is determined. The difference is calculated from the midpoint temperature to the outside ones. This temperature difference as a function of the distance from the center point corresponds to a quadratic function (3.3).

$$T - T_c = m * r^2 \quad (3.3)$$

The value of m can be determined by plotting the differential temperature $T - T_c$ versus the distance from the midpoint temperature, as seen in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Temperature difference about radial shifting

To determine the heat introduced or extracted $q \left[\frac{W}{kg} \right]$ at these temperature differences, the slope of the absorption or desorption is determined using a linear function. After converting the units, a value is obtained for the amount of hydrogen introduced per second.

$$q = \text{rate}H_2 * \Delta H \quad (3.4)$$

To determine the effective thermal conductivity $k_{eff} \left[\frac{W}{m \cdot K} \right]$, the amount of heat introduced, and the density of the material (ρ) are calculated in relation to the slope of the temperature difference as follows (3.5).

$$k_{eff} = \frac{q * \rho}{4 * m} \quad (3.5)$$

3.1.2 Activation Energy and frequency factor

In the subchapter, 3.2 Numerical Methods., the detailed expressions for the reaction kinetic are described. First, the temperature-dependent expression of the thermodynamic behavior of hydrogenation is briefly discussed in order to introduce the procedure of parameter estimation.

The reaction kinetics as a function of temperature is usually described by the Arrhenius equation (3.6).

$$K(T) = A \exp\left(\frac{-Ea}{RT}\right) \quad (3.6)$$

The only variable in this equation is temperature T . A describes the pre-exponential factor and Ea the activation energy of the material. R describes the universal gas constant. The activation energy provides information about the energy that must be overcome for the reaction to take place. The values for the pre-exponential factor as well as for the activation energy for almost every material can be taken from the literature.

The values determined for these constants in this work were also compared with the literature and checked for physical coherence. However, since every alloy can have deviations in its composition and a binder has been added to the pellet material, it makes sense to determine the values appropriately.

For the estimation of these parameters, a model was developed in the FEM software COMSOL. This model corresponds to a representation of a sample holder. The material was subjected to several absorption and desorption processes at a constant temperature of 40 °C and the constant pressure of 40 bars in the sample holder. These data were available in the research department. In the FEM model, the same boundary conditions were implemented and mathematically calculated based on the subchapter numerical methods and initial values for the activation energy and the pre-exponential factor known from the literature. A dimensionless ratio α , which is the hydrogen fraction, was determined from the experimental data of hydrogen loading in weight percent hydrogen. This is 0 when no hydrogen is absorbed and 1 when the maximum capacity is reached. As described by equation (3.7).

$$\alpha = \frac{m_0 - m_t}{m_0 - m_\infty} \quad (3.7)$$

Applying FEM simulation, a curve for the hydrogen fraction was also calculated. The parameter estimations aim is to approximate the simulated curve to the experimental curve by adjusting the activation energy and the preexponential factor. This was also carried out with the FEM software COMSOL. For this Optimization, the default setting BOBYQA (Bound Optimization by Quadratic Approximation) was used. This method is based on the principle of quadratic functions with the target function is approximated as best as possible. This is done in a region around the current iteration of the so-called trust region. The quadratic model is implemented

by minimizing the Frobenius norm and the difference in the Hessians of the two successive quadratic approximations [28].

3.1.3 Modeling geometries and mesh quality

For the creation of a digital model of a metal hydride tank, a step-by-step modeling process is applied, starting with a simple model, and working up to a model that is as complex as necessary, following the modeling strategy already mentioned. The basis of the geometry mapping is the already physically existing model of the HyCARE tank. The modeling strategy was derived from this model.

HyCARE tank

Figure 11 shows the HyCARE tank prototype, which reflects a first image of the planned tank, but not the final design for the HyCARE project. This prototype has already been built, and the absorption and desorption behavior has already been experimentally investigated. This model represents a reduced scale of the planned tank. Due to the experiments already carried out on this prototype, the modeling was carried out in the dimensions of the prototype in order to be able to compare it with experimental data.

Figure 11: HyCARE tank design

Sample Holder:

Figure 12 shows a representation of the volume occupied by the material inside the experimental sample holder. This model was used to estimate the kinetic parameters given by experimental results. Only the hydride bed in the center and the shell of the sample holder were considered. The diameter of 6 mm corresponds to the inner diameter of the sample holder used. The height of the hydride bed and thus the volume of the TiFeMn powder was calculated using its bulk density.

Figure 12: 3D-model of the sample holder: Intrinsic kinetics

Due to the simplicity of the geometry, meshing with simple tetrahedral elements is possible at a high quality, as can be seen in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Sample holder mesh statistic

2D-Model:

The 2D model, shown in Figure 14, represents a section of the tank along the z-axis and thus represents a radial simplification of the real tank. To reduce the calculation time, only a quarter of the circle was considered, and necessary symmetry boundary conditions were implemented. The hydrogen inlet represents a further simplification in this model. In the real tank it is located in the z-plane, but for the calculation of the free flow around the hydride bed, it had to be located in the x-y-plane. Furthermore, in this 2D model, no consideration of the cooling medium in the z-direction can be made. For this reason, the convective heat transfer coefficient was determined and implemented, considering the inflow data. In addition to the simplifications mentioned, this section does not represent a section in the flange area. This model was calculated with a free flow of hydrogen between hydrogen inlet and hydride bed using the Brinkman equation as well as with the Darcy law only in the hydride bed and the calculated values for the velocity field in the hydrogen domain.

Figure 14: 2D-model of the HyCARE tank

For the meshing of the 2D model of the HyCARE tank, a triangular meshing was chosen as shown in Figure 16. Considering the free flow of hydrogen in the gaseous hydrogen phase, boundary layers were also included. Figure 13 shows the mesh statistics, noting that the minimum element quality is > 0.1 , which according to [5] indicates reliable results.

Figure 15: 2D-model mesh statistic

Figure 16: Meshing 2D-model of the HyCARE tank

2D-axisymmetric model:

A 2D axisymmetric model was generated using a slice through the simplified 3D model (Figure 17). The tank has no rotational symmetry, but to verify the implemented assumptions, equations, initial and boundary conditions, it is reasonable to make this assumption. Compared to the 3D model, the calculation of the axisymmetric model is faster by a high factor. Due to the complexity of the flow field in free flow, the transport phenomena in this model were only studied using Darcy's law in the hydride bed. For the flow field in the hydrogen domain, approximated values from the 2D model were used.

Figure 17: 2D-axisymmetric model of the HyCARE tank

Since this section of the 3D model is also a complex geometry, an unstruck grid was used as seen in Figure 19. Triangular elements were used for this. In the flange area, the mesh is significantly coarser, as no calculation of a velocity field is necessary for this area, and the geometry there is simple. Since this section of the 3D model is also a complex geometry, an unstruck grid was used. Triangular elements were used for this. In the flange area, the mesh is significantly coarser, as no calculation of a velocity field is necessary for this area, and the geometry there is simple. The mesh has a high minimum element quality of 0.3805, which is shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18: Meshing statistic of 2D-axisymmetric model of the HyCARE tank

Figure 19: Meshing of 2D-axisymmetric model of the HyCARE tank

3D-Model:

The 3D model, shown in Figure 20, is the most realistic model and has a high complexity. However, this also leads to an intensive calculation effort. By quartering the geometry, symmetry effects are exploited, but compared to the assumed axis symmetry in the 2D axisymmetric model, this model represents a more realistic representation of the real tank. Compared to the original HyCARE tank, only a few simplifications can be found. In this 3D model, the pellets with their heat plates and the cooling pipes passing through the pellets are considered. The influence of the flanges on heat management is also considered. External connection elements for temperature measurement in the real tank were not considered.

Figure 20: 3D-Model of the HyCARE tank

Figure 21 shows the mesh quality for the 3D-model. The minimum element quality is with a value of 0.1487 higher than 0.1 and shows a reliable quality.

Figure 21: Meshing 3D-Model of the HyCARE tank

3.2 Numerical methods

Model Assumptions

The following assumptions were made for the simulation and modeling of the HyCARE tank:

- Hydrogen exists in a gaseous state and is calculated according to the ideal gas law
- The hydride material in the form of the TeFiMn pellet is taken as an isotropic and homogeneous porous medium.
- Local thermal equilibrium is assumed between the solid material and the hydrogen gas. The local temperature of the interphase of the gas and the material inside the vessel is the same.
- No convective material transport is assumed for the calculation of the concentration in the porous medium.
- The volume fraction changes as the change of porosity occurs upon hydrogenation and dehydrogenation processes
- For the 2D model, the convective heat coefficient is calculated to address the convective heat transfer between the cooling fluid and the hydride bed
- For the transport phenomena, the inertial term (Stokes flow) is neglected
- The gravitational force is neglected
- All model parameters and variables used for the tank simulations are fully described in Appendix A (Modeling Parameter)

Initial and boundary conditions

The initial and boundary conditions are implemented explicitly according to each physics: heat transport, intrinsic kinetics, and hydrogen transport.

Intrinsic Kinetics:

For the absorption, it is assumed that the initial condition is that the concentration of the reactants ($c_{reactants}$) is maximum while the concentration of the products ($c_{products}$) is zero.

As a boundary condition, a Neuman boundary condition is taken that in which the change in concentration at the edge of the hydride ($\frac{\partial c}{\partial t}$) bed is zero.

Initial:

Absorption

$$c_{reactants} = max.$$

$$c_{products} = 0$$

Desorption

$$c_{reactants} = 0$$

$$c_{products} = max$$

Boundary:

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} = 0$$

Heat transfer:

As initial conditions for the heat transport, it is assumed that the initial temperature of the solid phase is equal to that of the gaseous phase. Furthermore, the amount of heat introduced during absorption and the heat emitted at the beginning of desorption is zero. For the boundary conditions, it is set that the variable temperature is equal to the temperature of the external wall. It is also set that the amount of heat introduced or removed depends on the transport of hydrogen and that the amount of heat absorbed conductively by the cooling tubes is equal to the amount of convective heat removed to the cooling liquid.

Initial:

$$T_{initial} = T_g$$

$$qw = c * \Delta H * r' = 0$$

Boundary:

$$T = T_{external\ wall}$$

$$(c_p \rho T)_g (\vec{u}_g)|_{inlet} = -k_{eff} \vec{\nabla} T + (c_p \rho T)_g (\vec{u}_g)|_{inside}$$

$$-k \nabla T|_T = h(T - T_{cooling\ Fluid})$$

Hydrogen Transport

As initial conditions for the transport of hydrogen through the porous filter in free flow to the porous hydride bed, different ramp functions are applied for absorption/desorption until the maximum/minimum operating pressure is reached, depending on the experimental conditions of the HyCARE tank. As a boundary condition, it is assumed that the pressure gradient at the edge of the reservoir is zero and the change in velocity at the edge of the reservoir is also zero.

Initial:

$$p_{inlet/outlet} = F(t)$$

Boundary:

$$\nabla p = 0$$

$$\rho \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = 0$$

Governing equations

The following equations and physical relationships apply to the hydride bed to describe the hydrogenation/dehydrogenation process. They have no validity in the area of the tank shell or insulation.

Energy balance:

With the assumption that there is a thermal equilibrium between the gas phase and the solid phase in the hydride, the equation (3.8) can represent the system's energy balance [20].

$$(\rho C_p) \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} - \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(k_{eff} \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right) = -\dot{m} [\Delta H + T(C_{pg} - C_{ps})] \quad (3.8)$$

Here describes T the temperature, (ρC_p) is the effective thermal capacity, k_{eff} is the effective thermal conductivity, ΔH is the enthalpy of reaction and \dot{m} is the source/sink term.

Kinetics:

The description of the kinetic behavior during hydrogenation/dehydrogenation is expressed by equations (3.9),(3.10).

$$\dot{m}_{Abs} = A \exp\left(-\frac{Ea}{RT}\right) \left(\frac{P - P_{eq}}{P_{eq}}\right) \left(\frac{3}{2} \left((1 - \alpha)^{-\frac{1}{3}} - 1\right)\right) \quad (3.9)$$

$$\dot{m}_{Des} = A \exp\left(-\frac{Ea}{RT}\right) \left(\frac{P_{eq} - p}{p_{eq}}\right) \left(\frac{3}{2} \left((1 - \alpha)^{-\frac{1}{3}} - 1\right)\right) \quad (3.10)$$

It is possible to calculate the driving force of the reaction rate as a quotient of the difference between the operative and equilibrium pressure and the equilibrium pressure according to [22].

The determination of $G(\alpha)$ depends on the material and can either be taken from the literature or determined by fitting the kinetic curves. In this work, the following rate-limiting step is taken (3.11) based on the fitting of experimental curves, as seen in Appendix B Curve fitting of the kinetic behavior (Gas-solid).

$$G(\alpha) = \frac{3}{2} \left((1 - \alpha)^{-\frac{1}{3}} - 1\right) \quad (3.11)$$

It is a 4D rate-limiting step, since it does not depend on the shape of the particles [15]

Momentum equation:

The gases velocity through the porous filter, the porous hydride bed, and the free flow between them is expresses by the Brinkman equation. By neglecting the gravitational effect, the equation which gives the velocity of gas inside the tank is given by equation (3.12) [17].

$$\rho \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \nabla[-pI + K] - \left(\mu k^{-1} + \beta \varepsilon \rho u + \frac{Q_m}{\varepsilon^2}\right) u + F \quad (3.12)$$

For the simulation of the sample holder and the calculation of specific models, Darcy's law was used to determine the velocity in the hydride bed, as seen in equation (3.13).

$$u = -\frac{K}{\mu} \nabla p \quad (3.13)$$

Equilibrium pressure:

There are various approaches to describing the equilibrium pressure. On the one hand, the equilibrium pressure can be described by the van't Hoff equation (2.4) without considering the plateau slope as a function of temperature. This is the same for hydrogenation and dehydrogenation. On the other hand, there are also material-dependent expressions for describing the equilibrium pressure as a function of temperature and hydrogen loading as shown in equation (3.14) from [22].

Absorption/Desorption:

$$peq = \frac{10\alpha}{1 + 10\alpha} (\exp(\alpha_0 T^{-1} + \alpha_1 T + T^2 + \alpha_3 \alpha + \alpha_4 \alpha^2 + \alpha_5 \alpha^3) + \exp(\beta_0 T + \beta_1 T^2 + \beta_2 T \alpha + \alpha_3 + \beta_3 \alpha + \beta_4 \alpha^2) + \exp(50(\alpha - \beta_5)) \alpha_2) \quad (3.14)$$

Coefficient	Absorption/Desorption	Coefficient	Absorption/Desorption
α_0	-2793 / -2506	β_0	-0.08377 / -0.1186
α_1	0.05211 / 0.0329	β_1	8.617e-5 / 3.193e-4
α_2	-7.184e-5 / -3.011e-5	β_2	0.04009 / 0.01629
α_3	2.3760 / 4.124	β_3	5.804 / -20.42
α_4	-0.3568 / -2.964	β_4	-3.313 / 11.89
α_5	-0.2035 / 0.961	β_5	1.735 / 1.74

Table 2: Table of coefficient for equilibrium pressure [22]

4 Results and Discussion

This chapter is divided into two subchapters. The first subchapter deals with the experimentally determined results of this work. The results for the kinetic parameters and the thermodynamic parameters are presented and discussed. These experimentally determined parameters have been included in the developed models. The simulative results categorically subdivide to the geometry level from 2D to 2D axisymmetric to 3D. The simulative results are compared with the experimental results to verify the validity of the experimental results as well as the simulative assumptions. For the 2D model as well as for the 2D axisymmetric model, parameters and geometry variation were also calculated.

4.1 Experimental parameter determination of a TiFeMn solid-state hydrogen storage tank

4.1.1 Kinetic parameter

Absorption

In Figure 22, with the green diamonds, the absorption curve for the TiFeMn powder for cycle 3 can be seen. The blue line shows the simulative curve after the parametric estimation for the absorption. It can be clearly seen that the simulative approach follows the experimental behavior. 40 bar was taken as the operating pressure for the simulation. This corresponds to the absorption pressure from the experimental setup. The temperature of 40 °C was also taken from the experimental setup. With these initial and boundary conditions and the numerical model of the simulation, the values for the activation energy and the pre-exponential factor were determined for the parameter estimation for the absorption, as shown in Table 3

Parameter	Value
Operating Pressure	40 bar
Temperature	40 °C
Enthalpy	-29.6 kJ/mol
Entropy	-131 J/mol*K
Activation Energy	25.8 kJ/mol
Frequency Factor	95 1/s

Table 3: Absorption parameters for kinetic parameter estimation

These values are within a physically reasonable range and represent similar values for TiFeMn alloys.

Figure 22: Absorption kinetic parameter estimation

Desorption

The parameter estimation for desorption can be seen in Figure 23. Here the green diamonds show the experimental results for the first cycle and the red stars show the experimental results for the third cycle. The blue curve corresponds to the simulated results of the parameter estimation. The experiment as well as the simulation, were again performed at 40 °C. The operating pressure corresponds to 1 bar. It can be seen that at the beginning of the desorption the simulated results correspond to the values of the 3rd cycle. This is followed by a period of 2-4 min in which the simulated results lie between cycles 1 and 3, until the simulated curve follows the values of cycle 1. The simulated results for desorption also correspond to the real experimentally determined desorption behavior. Table 4 shows the initial conditions as well as the thermodynamic parameters and the estimated parameter for this curve fitting.

Parameter	Value
Operative Pressure	1 bar
Temperature	40 °C
Enthalpy	30.2 kJ/mol
Entropy	-128 J/mol*K
Activation Energy	12.8 kJ/mol
Frequency Factor	122.4 1/s

Table 4: Absorption parameters for kinetic parameter estimation

These values for the activation energy and the pre-exponential factor represent a physically reasonable range and similar values for TiFeMn alloys in powder form.

Figure 23: Desorption kinetic parameter estimation

4.1.2 Heat transfer parameters

Effective thermal conductivity

An equation for effective thermal conductivity as a function of temperature was determined for absorption and desorption. A temperature range of 30-70 degrees Celsius was selected. This range corresponds to the operational range of the tank. The exact measurement procedure was explained in chapter 3, experimental methods. In Figure 24, the prepared sample is shown after the cycles. In the marked area, a small dent can be seen, this is the imprint of one of the temperatures couples of the sample holder. This shows that the temperature couples were very well embedded in the hydride bed. This is extremely important, otherwise, the measurement results would not have been so accurate, as the proportion of gaseous hydrogen would then have been higher in terms of thermal conductivity. It is also clear that the sample is still highly stable after the hydrogenation and dehydrogenation processes. This is again an interesting aspect regarding the removal of hydrogenated pellets by new ones.

Figure 24: Sample after cycling

Figure 25 again illustrates the procedure for determining the effective thermal conductivity. The 4 radially shifted temperature curves and the desorption curve for the temperature range 50 degrees C are shown. These curves were generated for the range 30-70 degrees Celsius. The desorption curve can be used to determine the amount of heat introduced or dissipated, and the temperature peaks provide information on the range in which the desorption curve must be evaluated. Figure 25 also shows how the temperature curve in the hydride bed behaves as a function of the radial position. It is assumed that the heat only spreads in the radial direction. In the case of desorption, the lowest temperatures are to be expected in the center of the hydride bed. This then increases with distance from the center. For absorption, the highest temperatures are expected in the center of the hydride bed. The sample holder is made of a highly conductive material, up to 200-250 (W/m*K), to prevent wall edge effects. The extremely

high conductivity ensures that during absorption the heat can be quickly transferred to the cooling system and during desorption, the heat can be quickly transferred from the cooling system to the hydride bed. This ensures a clear representation of the temperature behavior without delays.

Figure 25: Temperature peak and desorption curve for 50 °C

Absorption:

The values for the effective thermal conductivity for absorption plotted against temperature are shown in Figure 26. These values are in the range of 7-12 [W/m*K], depending on the temperature. For the same material in powder form, values for normal thermal conductivity around 3 [W/m*K] were obtained [13]. For this highly compact alloy, values above 3 W/m*K are to be expected. The values for the effective thermal conductivity for highly compact MH are thus also within a range of reference MH materials [24]. All calculation procedure for the effective thermal conductivity upon hydrogenation is explained in Appendix C: Fitting of effective thermal conductivity and example calculation

By fitting the experimental values with a quadratic approach, the following equation (4.1) for the effective thermal conductivity as a function of temperature can be used.

$$k_{eff\,abs} = 2.9695 + 0.12045 T + 2.26061 \cdot 10^{-4} T^2 \quad (4.1)$$

Figure 26: Fitting for effective thermal conductivity of absorption

Desorption:

A temperature range of 30-70 degrees Celsius was also chosen to determine the effective thermal conductivity during desorption. Figure 27 shows the values for the effective thermal conductivity plotted against temperature. Again, a quadratic function was fitted to account for the temperature-dependent behavior of the effective thermal conductivity.

Here, too, the values are higher than the values determined for the thermal conductivity in powder form and in a similar range to the values from [24].

Equation (4.2) describes the quadratic and temperature-dependent behavior of the effective thermal conductivity for a temperature range of 30-70 degrees Celsius. All calculation procedure for the effective thermal conductivity upon dehydrogenation is explained in Appendix C: Fitting of effective thermal conductivity and example calculation

$$k_{eff_{des}} = 8.66829 + 0.00576 T + 4.92685 \cdot 10^{-4} T^2 \quad (4.2)$$

Figure 27: Fitting for effective thermal conductivity of desorption

4.1.3 Thermodynamic parameters

Reaction enthalpy and entropy determination

Figure 28 shows the pressure concentration isotherms (PCI) from the real tank. From these curves, points of different concentrations and temperatures were taken. By interpolation between the points, an equilibrium pressure was determined for each point of the capacity. Using the van't Hoff equation, values for enthalpy and entropy were determined. For enthalpy, a function was determined for both absorption and desorption as a function of hydrogen loading. Average values were determined for the entropy. All calculations procedures for the enthalpy and entropy determination upon hydrogenation and dehydrogenation are explained in Appendix D: Fitting of Enthalpy and Entropy from PCI's

Figure 28: PCI curves from experimental set-up [13]

Absorption

Figure 29 shows the approximated function for the enthalpy of reaction as a function of hydrogen loading. It corresponds to a value of -32 kJ/mol at the beginning of the absorption, when the hydrogen charge is zero. It reaches a saddle point around the value of -25 kJ/mol at about half the hydrogen loading and tends towards -22 kJ/mol when reaching the maximum loading of about 1.2 weight percent hydrogen.

Equation (4.3) shows the cubic behavior of the enthalpy of reaction as a function of hydrogen loading.

$$\Delta H_{abs} = -32.29 + 34.16 \alpha - 53.20 \alpha^2 + 26.15 \alpha^3 \quad (4.3)$$

Figure 29: Experimental DeltaH for Absorption

Figure 30 is given as a reference model. This is also a TiFeMn alloy. The values for the enthalpy of reaction are in a similar range, but the behavior of the reference model is quadratic. For the reference model, however, the alloy was in powder form and without additional binders.

Figure 30: Reference DeltaH Absorption [22]

Desorption

Figure 31 shows the reaction enthalpy curve for desorption. The reaction enthalpy in kJ/mol is plotted against the hydrogen loading in weight percent. As in the case of absorption, a cubic approximation was used to determine the behavior of the reaction enthalpy as a function of the hydrogen loading.

Equation (4.4) represents the cubic behavior of the enthalpy of reaction as a function of the hydrogen content.

$$\Delta H_{des} = -26.58 + 17.59wt\% - 44.33wt\%^2 + 18.43 wt\%^3 \quad (4.4)$$

Figure 31: Experimental DeltaH for Desorption

Figure 32 shows the reference model provided from [22]. The values are again in a similar range and the curve also shows similar behavior.

Figure 32: Reference DeltaH Desorption [22]

4.2 Simulation and experimental validation of a TiFeMn solid state hydrogen storage tank

4.2.1 2D-Model; Comparison with experimental results and parametric optimization

Absorption

Comparison with experimental results

Figure 33 and Figure 34 show the comparison of the experimental results with the simulated results.

In Figure 33, the hydrogen fractionation is plotted. At a value of 1, the largest possible amount of hydrogen is stored in the MH. At a value of 0, no hydrogen is present in the MH. The blue line represents the simulated results, and the green line the experimentally determined measuring points from the real HyCARE tank. The kinetic and thermodynamic parameters and equations for describing the material behavior described above have been incorporated into the simulation, and additional parameters and formulas for describing the hydrogenation process can be found in the Appendix A.

Figure 33 shows that at the beginning of the absorption process, the simulated course of absorption is slower than the experimental course. From about 83 minutes, the trend changes, and the simulated absorption runs faster than the experimentally performed absorption. However, the simulation reflects an exactly accurate image of the real tank. Even though the model is a significant simplification.

Figure 33: Experimental comparison from 2D-model absorption for hydrogen fraction about time

Figure 34 shows the comparison of the temperature curves in the hydride bed from the experimentally determined temperatures and the simulated results. The blue line again represents the simulated results, and the green line the comparison to the experimentally determined measured values. At the beginning of the absorption, both temperatures increase rapidly due to the exothermic reaction when hydrogen is stored in the MH. The green line of the experimentally determined results reaches the maximum at about 86 degrees Celsius within about 30 minutes. After reaching the maximum value, the experimental course flattens out again very quickly and tends towards the value 50 degrees Celsius, which corresponds to the temperature of the cooling liquid. The blue line of the simulated results shows a somewhat different course. At the beginning of absorption, the temperature rises somewhat more slowly and does not reach the characteristic peak temperature value of 86 degrees Celsius, but instead reaches a temperature of about 72 degrees Celsius.

On the other hand, this temperature is maintained significantly longer than in the experimental curve. However, it must be considered that the cooling system was simplified in the 2D model. Instead of the pipe flow in the z-direction, a convective heat transfer coefficient was determined, taking into account the flow velocity of the cooling liquid and the pipe diameter. This was then implemented in the simulation as a heat flow with the external temperature from the almost constant temperature of the experimental setup. As with the hydrogen fraction curve, the temperature of the simulated result intersects the curve of the experimental results at approximately 83 minutes. From this point on, the absorption of the simulation is faster than the absorption of the experimental setup. As a result, the temperature of the simulated results is also higher than the temperature of the experimental results from this point on. However,

since the simulative absorption is then completed faster than the experimental simulation, the simulative absorption reaches the temperature of the cooling system of 50 degrees Celsius faster.

Figure 34: Experimental comparison from 2D-model absorption for hydride temperature about time

Parametric optimization

After showing that for the 2D model of the absorption, the simulated results and the experimental results are in a similar range, a parameter variation was performed to find optimal parameters for the operation of the HyCARE tank and to detect possible limitations. Three main parameters were varied. The temperature of the cooling liquid, the operating pressure and the velocity of the cooling liquid were varied. For each parameter variation, the values from the experimental setup were selected for the other two parameters. To compare the different parameter variations, the variation is plotted on the x-axis and the y-axis the amount of hydrogen absorbed in weight percent after a time of 60 minutes. All the graphs of the wt.% vs. time are shown in Appendix E.

Figure 35 shows the variation of the temperature of the coolant. The temperature of the coolant was varied between 20-60 degrees Celsius. A very linear course is shown, and no limitation is evident in this range of variation. The lower the temperature selected, the better the heat can be dissipated during the exothermic reaction. This means that the reaction can proceed more quickly since the difference between the temperature-dependent equilibrium pressure and the

operative pressure is greater. At a coolant temperature of 20 degrees Celsius, 0.875 percent by weight of hydrogen can already be absorbed within 60 minutes. On the other hand, at a coolant temperature of 60 degrees Celsius, only a scant 0.55 percent by weight of hydrogen can be absorbed in 60 minutes. Due to the linear course of the variation, no optimum temperature can be selected for the coolant. It depends primarily on which temperature can be provided most favorably from outside, for example, depending on the waste heat of the fuel cell.

Figure 35: Cooling temperature optimization for 2D-model absorption

Figure 36 represents the variation of the operative pressure for absorption. The pressure was varied in a range of 20-40 bar. The coolant temperature was selected with the default setting of 50 degrees Celsius and the speed of the coolant was also selected with the default setting of 0.3 m/s. With the variation of the operating pressure, a step shape can be seen in the course. Thus, the effect of increasing the pressure from 30 bar to 35 bar is more pronounced in the amount of hydrogen absorbed in 60 minutes than the increase from 25 bar to 30 bar. The increase from 35 bar to 40 bar also brings only a smaller increase in the amount of hydrogen absorbed in 60 minutes.

In this variation, it is easier to find an optimization of the varied parameter. The pressure in the experimental setup is 30 bar. An increase of the pressure by 5 bars to 35 bars would increase the absorbed hydrogen by 20% in 60 min.

Again, the reason for the faster absorption is the difference between operative pressure and equilibrium pressure.

Figure 36: Operative pressure optimization for 2D-model absorption

Figure 37 shows the variation of the coolant velocity. In order to be able to vary the velocity in this 2D model, the equation for determining the convective heat transfer coefficient was implemented. This coefficient is calculated as a function $f(\text{Re}, \text{Pr}, \text{Nu})$, thus the value for the convective heat transfer coefficient depends on the coolant's velocity. Plotted on the x-axis is the variation of the velocity of the coolant from 0-10 m/s. On the y-axis against the amount of hydrogen in weight percent that was absorbed after 60 minutes. The curve shows a quite cross-sectional course. When the speed of the coolant increases from 0.1 m/s to 0.2 m/s, the absorbed hydrogen increases from 0.59 wt% to 0.642 wt%, i.e., an increase of 8%. From a speed of 5 m/s, the curve flattens out considerably and a further increase in speed only results in a more minor increase in the amount of hydrogen absorbed in 60 minutes. Doubling the speed of the coolant from 5 m/s to 10 m/s only results in an increase in the absorbed hydrogen from 0.81 wt% to 0.84 wt% in 60 minutes, i.e., an increase of 4%. Therefore, it must then be considered separately whether the increase in velocity is still necessary for this range and, if so, at what cost this increase implies.

Again, the main reason for the faster absorption after 60 minutes is the difference between the equilibrium pressure and the operative pressure. With an increase in the velocity of the coolant, the heat of reaction can be dissipated better, and the equilibrium pressure does not increase as much as with a comparatively lower velocity of the coolant.

An optimum speed of the coolant can be 2 m/s. Above 2 m/s, the curve flattens significantly and the advantage of faster absorption to increase the speed of the coolant decreases significantly. In the end, the decisive factor here is also what can be provided in the system combination of MH tank, fuel cell, or loading-discharging device as an intermediate storage system, or what temperatures or loading and unloading times are required.

Figure 37: Cooling fluid velocity optimization for 2D-model absorption

Table 5 shows the results of the parametric optimization and the values of the parameters from the experimental setup for the 2D model of absorption.

	Experimental	Optimization
Coolant temperature	50 (degC)	40 (degC)
Operative Pressure	30 (bar)	35 (bar)
Coolant velocity	0.3 (m/s)	2 (m/s)

Table 5: Optimized parameter for 2D-model absorption

Desorption

Comparison with experimental results

Figure 38 and Figure 39 show the comparison of the simulated results for desorption with the 2D model with the experimental results of desorption from the HyCARE tank.

Figure 38 shows the hydrogen defraction over time. At the value of 1, no hydrogen has yet been desorbed, i.e., the MH is entirely saturated. At a value of 0, the hydrogen is completely desorbed, and no more hydrogen is stored in the MH. The blue line shows the simulated results and the green line the experimental measuring points. At the beginning of desorption up to a value of 0.7, the curves are remarkably similar. The simulation runs faster than the experimental process from 0.7 to 0.2 of the de hydrogen fraction to 0.2 defraction. From the value of 0.2 the simulation is again slower than the experiment. In total, however, the simulation with the 2D model mimics the behavior of the HyCARE tank well.

Figure 38: Experimental comparison from 2D-model desorption for hydrogen fraction about time

Figure 39 can be used to compare the temperatures between simulation and experiment of the endothermic reaction of hydrogen removal in the MH. The blue line shows the temperature curve in the hydride bed, and the green line the curve in the hydride bed of the HyCARE tank. There is a direct correspondence between the curves. The simulation reaches in the

approximately identical period the minimum temperature as in the experiment. The minimum temperature in the hydride bed of the HyCARE tank is about 37 degrees Celsius and the minimum temperature in the simulation is about 31 degrees Celsius. The heat for the endothermic reaction cannot be provided as quickly or effectively in the 2D model. After reaching the minimum temperature, the simulation as well as the experimental curve reach the value of the temperature of the coolant of 50 degrees Celsius.

Figure 39: Experimental comparison from 2D-model desorption for hydride temperature about time

As with the 2D model of absorption, the 2D model of desorption mimics the behavior of the HyCARE tank very well, so that parameter optimization can provide reliable results.

Parametric optimization

A parameter variation was also performed for desorption in the 2D model for the three variables of coolant temperature, operative pressure, and coolant velocity. These are plotted in their variations on the x-axis and on the y-axis is plotted how many weight percent hydrogen could be desorbed in 60 minutes. Here, too, the parameter variation should provide information on whether there are limiting values for the varied parameters for desorption, or whether even a

minor adjustment can have a significant effect. All the graphs of the wt.% vs. time are shown in Appendix E.

Figure 40 shows the variation of the temperature of the coolant. It was varied between 20-80 degrees Celsius. As already seen with the absorption, a very linear course can be seen here as well. The endothermic reaction of desorption needs heat to take place. If only a coolant temperature of 20 degrees Celsius can be provided, only 0.2 percent by weight of the hydrogen is desorbed after 60 minutes.

In contrast to a coolant temperature of 80 degrees Celsius, at which about 0.65 percent by weight of hydrogen could be desorbed after 60 minutes. In principle, no limitation can be seen in this temperature range. If the temperature is reduced further than 20 degrees Celsius, then sufficient heat can no longer be supplied, and the reaction will stop. Whether the linear progression of the increase in the desorbed amount of hydrogen in 60 minutes continues above 80 degrees Celsius must be checked. For the time being, no optimum temperature of the coolant can be selected for the selected temperature range. Increasing the temperature results in faster desorption, but also requires more energy.

The temperature to be used for the coolant should therefore be adapted to the tank requirements. If the tank is operated with a fuel cell, there is a temperature range which supplies the tank. The temperature depends on how cheaply it can be provided or how quickly it has to be desorbed for use as a stationary storage tank.

Figure 40: Cooling temperature optimization for 2D-model desorption

The variation of the operating pressure and the influence on the desorbed amount of hydrogen after 60 min can be seen in figure 41. The pressure varies from 2.75-10 bar. This directly influences the pressure difference between the operating pressure and the equilibrium pressure and thus on the speed of the reaction. A strong linear behavior can be seen, the lower the pressure is chosen, the more hydrogen can be desorbed in 60 minutes. From a pressure of about 7 bar, the reaction slowly comes to a standstill and no further hydrogen is desorbed. Here, too, it is not possible to identify a necessarily optimal pressure, but it does show the limitation because no hydrogen is desorbed at an operating pressure of 10 bar. However, in terms of coupling the simulated tank with a fuel cell, it is possible to notice that operative overpressure between 5-10 bar would lead a poor hydrogenation performance. Therefore, it would be demanding to invest more energy to increase the tank's temperature so that the tank can provide more hydrogen if the operative overpressure lays between 5 and 10 bar, which is a standard range of the commercial fuel cells.

Figure 41: Operative pressure optimization for 2D-model desorption

Figure 42 shows the variation in the velocity of the coolant. Here, the coolant velocity varies from 0.1-15 m/s. The steepest increase can be seen from 0-2 m/s. From 2-4 m/s the curve flattens out more and from 4-10 m/s, even more. From the coolant velocity of 10 m/s, only a slight acceleration of the desorption can be detected. The speed of the coolant has a direct

influence on how much heat can be made available to the reaction. This then ensures a faster reaction. An increase in velocity of 10-15 m/s has only a 3% increase in desorption rate.

Here it is easier to select an optimal parameter. The cooling medium velocity should be between 2-4 m/s to ensure an optimum desorption velocity.

Figure 42: Cooling fluid velocity optimization for 2D-model desorption

Table 6 shows which parameters were used to operate the HyCARE tank and in which areas optimization and operation are also possible.

	Experimental	Optimization
Coolant temperature	50 (degC)	40-50 (degC)
Operative Pressure	2.75 (bar)	2.75-5(bar)
Coolant velocity	0.3 (m/s)	2-4 (m/s)

Table 6: Optimized parameter for 2D-model desorption

4.2.2 2D-axisymmetric-Model; Comparison with experimental results and parametric optimization

Absorption

Comparison with experimental results

Figure 43 and figure 44 show the simulative comparison of the 2D axisymmetric model for absorption with the experimental data from the HyCARE tank. Again, the goal is to use the experimental results for the kinetic and thermodynamic behavior of the material, implement this in the simulation, and mimic the HyCARE tank's behavior as closely as possible.

Figure 43 shows the simulated course of the hydrogen fraction compared to the experimental data from the HyCARE tank. At the beginning of the absorption, the simulation runs faster than the actual absorption in the HyCARE tank. Similar to the 2D model, the simulative curve intersects the experimental curve and reaches the maximum hydrogen fraction faster. Nevertheless, simulation and reality are close to each other.

Figure 43: Experimental comparison from 2D-axisymmetric model absorption for hydrogen fraction

Figure 44 shows the temperature curve in the hydride bed for the simulation and the experimental data from the HyCARE tank. The green line shows the experimental data that quickly reaches the maximum of 88 degrees Celsius. Compared to the 2D model, the 2D axisymmetric model, shown with the blue line, shows a slightly different temperature behavior. It reaches the peak of the temperature with 69 degrees Celsius in the same period as the experimental results. However, the simulation reaches the temperature of the coolant much faster than the experimental curve. However, it must be considered that the 2D-axisymmetric model entails a larger surface area of the cooling system due to the rotational symmetry that does not exist in reality. This means that the heat of absorption can be dissipated in a better way.

Figure 44: Experimental comparison from 2D-model absorption for hydride temperature

Parametric Optimization

For the 2D axisymmetric model of absorption, a parametric optimization was also performed. In this case, however, no operating parameters were changed, but an attempt was made to optimize the geometry. Here, too, the aim was to find optimal geometry adjustments or to determine limitations. The results of the parametric variation for absorption did not reproduce the same values as the experimental data of the HyCARE tank, but they mimicked the same

behavior. This leads to the conclusion that geometry optimization can also mimic the behavior of the tank.

As a first geometry optimization, the height of the pellets was changed. This was selected because this optimization can also be imitated in the HyCARE tank with little effort. Only more or fewer heat plates have to be installed. Figure 45 shows the different pellet sizes. The HyCARE test set-up has a loading of 24 pellets. The simulation with 6 pellets therefore has 4 times the height of the pellets than the loading with 24 pellets. This means that the same mass of hydride material is always present in the tank to provide a reliable comparison. Thus, the simulation with 48 pellets has half the height of the simulation with 24 pellets. The red dot marks the location in the hydride bed where the comparative values for hydrogen fraction and temperature were taken.

Figure 45: Comparison of pellet size

Figure 46 now represents the variation of pellet size in comparison to hydrogen fraction and hydride bed temperature. The curves with the star show the behavior of the absorption with 6 pellets in the tank. The curves with the plus sign show the behavior for 24 pellets, and the curves with the square sign show the behavior with 48 pellets. In the left part of the diagram,

the curves of the temperature curve can be seen. From bottom left to top right, the three curves show the characteristic picture of hydrogen fractionation during absorption.

Figure 46: Pellet size optimization for 2D-axisymmetric model absorption

The red curve of the temperature curve marked with the star for 6 pellets shows a significantly higher peak temperature than the curves for 24 or even 48 pellets. Since the loading with 6 pellets has a significantly smaller surface area than the loading with more pellets, the heat can be dissipated much more poorly during absorption. As a result, the equilibrium pressure is also higher due to the higher temperature, and thus the difference between equilibrium pressure and operating pressure decreases and the reaction proceeds more slowly, as shown in figure 47.

This can be seen in the yellow curve of the hydrogen fractionation marked with a star. This shows how the higher temperature affects the reaction kinetics. Nevertheless, it is only minimally below the curve with the 24 pellets. Although the number of pellets was reduced by a factor of 4, the effect is not as enormous. Quite the opposite of the comparison with 24 pellets and 48 pellets. The temperature profile, shown with a green curve for 24 pellets and a blue curve for 48 pellets, shows a similar difference as with 24 pellets and 6 pellets. But in the curves of hydrogen fractionation, shows a significantly greater difference of the speed of absorption of 48 pellets in turquoise and 24 pellets in purple. The diagram shows that there is no proportional behavior of the change in pellet size with respect to reaction behavior.

Figure 47: Pellet size optimization for 2D-axisymmetric model absorption pressure

In summary, the pellet size clearly affects the temperature behavior and thus also the speed of the reaction. However, there is no direct proportionality, so that with the variation of further pellet sizes, the optimal pellet size can be found, depending on the requirements. However, a change in the height of the pellet also affects the stability and the loading effort. It takes much longer to load the tank with many narrow pellets, and since the material is very brittle, the risk of breaking when loading or unloading the pellets increases. On the other hand, the thicker pellets are easier to handle and will also be much more stable. Furthermore, compared to the behavior with 24 pellets, it also shows only a slight slowdown of the reaction behavior.

Desorption

Comparison with experimental results

For the desorption process, a 2D-axisymmetric model was developed. The comparison with the experimental data of the HyCARE tank and the parametric optimization were carried out.

Figure 48 shows the comparison of hydrogen dehydration for the simulation, blue curve, and the experimental data from the HyCARE tank, green curve. Again, the behavior is similar to the absorption of the 2D-axisymmetric model. There is a larger surface area of the cooling

system and therefore better heat can be provided for the endothermic reaction, which leads to a faster reaction process.

Figure 48: Experimental comparison from 2D-axisymmetric model desorption for hydrogen fraction

Figure 49 illustrates the behavior of the faster reaction due to the better temperature behavior described above. The peak temperature in the simulation only reaches a value of 41 degrees Celsius compared to operation in the HyCARE tank where a peak temperature of 36.5 degrees Celsius was reached. The temperature of the coolant is also reached again more quickly.

This approach again leads to a, therefore, a more significant difference between equilibrium pressure and operating pressure and thus faster reaction kinetic behavior.

Figure 49: Experimental comparison from 2D-axisymmetric model desorption for hydride temperature

Parametric Optimization

A parameter fit for the 2D-axisymmetric model was performed based on the parameter variation of the 2D model of desorption. For this purpose, the optimal parameters presented in table 6 were used. The velocity of the coolant was chosen to be 2 m/s, the temperature of the coolant to be 50 degrees Celsius, and the operating pressure to be 4.3 bar.

As can be seen in figure 50, the reaction is faster with the adjusted parameters. The increased velocity of the coolant from 0.3 m/s to 2 m/s even compensates for the higher pressure from 2.75 bar to 4.3 bar.

Figure 50: Parametric optimization for 2D-axisymmetric model desorption for hydrogen fraction

The behavior described above for the hydrogen dehydration curve is also evident in figure 51 for the temperature behavior. Due to the higher speed of the coolant, a low peak temperature is not reached in the first place. The heat transport is significantly better, and the coolant temperature is also reached again more quickly.

Figure 51: Parametric optimization for 2D-axisymmetric model desorption for hydride temperature

4.2.3 3D-Model; Comparison with experimental results

The results of the 3D model were created in collaboration with the supervisor of this work, *Dr. Julián Puszkiel*.

In the case of the 3D-model, the hydrogenation model was performed. As seen in Figure 52, the wt.% vs time is represented. The experimental curve is slower than the simulated one, though the correlation between the simulated and the experimental results are good. In Figure 53 the equilibrium and operative pressure are shown.

Figure 52: Experimental comparison from 3D-model absorption for hydrogen fraction

Figure 53: Experimental comparison from 3D-model absorption for the pressure

Figure 52 shows that the simulation presents a faster hydrogen absorption than the experimental results. In Figure 53 it is possible to note that the driving force at the beginning of the hydrogenation follows almost the equilibrium pressure of the hydride, resulting in a slow absorption. After 10 minutes, the pressure increases over the equilibrium pressure and thus the hydrogenation speeds up. This behavior depicts a large driving force given by the difference between the operative and equilibrium pressure. This difference is less notable in the experimental setup due to the more abrupt rise of temperature. This behavior can directly result from an overestimated convective heat transfer coefficient between the cooling pipe and the hydride bed. Moreover, the operative pressure ramp was assumed to increase linearly, representing a certain deviation of the experimental ramp of pressure. These factors might account for the difference between the experimental and the simulation result. Despite this fact, the digital model, including all the thermodynamic, kinetic, heat transfer, and transport dependencies, shows a good correlation with the reality, considering the complexity of the model.

5 Conclusion and Prospect

5.1 Conclusion

This work aimed to create a digital model of a hydrogen storage tank based on room temperature hydrides and work out possible parameter and geometric optimizations. A developed test set-up of the HyCARE tank was utilized to couple the modeling results and the experimental outcomes. Creating a digital twin's development allows understanding the phenomena happening during the hydrogenation and dehydrogenation processes. Furthermore, the validation of the model by comparing with experimental results opens the possibility for further optimization of the design based on simulations, an approach that provides a notable advantage from the required time and cost standpoint. Modifying the experimental set up and planning experiments demand higher costs and more significant times.

In order to mimic the behavior of the real tank as closely as possible, experimental investigations were also carried out with the pellet-shaped hydride material. For this purpose, values were determined for the kinetic and thermodynamic behavior of the material so that these could then be incorporated into the simulation. Many of these experimentally determined data were not yet available for this material and therefore had to be determined before the simulation. Since the kinetic behavior is an essential parameter for the course of the reaction and only a few reference values are available for the TiFeMn alloy, values for the kinetic parameters were determined. For this purpose, kinetic curves of powdered material of the TiFeMn alloy were already available in the research department. Based on these experimentally obtained data, parameter estimation was carried out. For this purpose, COMSOL FEM software was used to create a sample holder in which the hydride bed matches the dimensions of the experimental loading of the sample holder. The experimentally determined curves for hydrogen hydration/dehydration were then approximated using Bound Optimization by Quadratic Approximation, and values for activation energy and frequency factor were determined.

In reference to the thermodynamic behavior, values for the enthalpy and entropy of reaction for the material were subtracted from experimental data. For the enthalpy of reaction, only average values were available, but since the enthalpy changes strongly with increasing hydrogen loading or unloading, values for the enthalpy were determined from existing PCI's and the van't Hoff equation in relation to the loading state and determined with a fitting equation as a function of the hydrogen loading. Since the functions for entropy exhibited somewhat contradictory physical behavior, average values were determined for them.

Regarding the heat transfer phenomena, the effective thermal conductivity was determined. No values have yet been determined for the effective thermal conductivity of this pellet-shaped material. However, since the effective thermal conductivity has a significant influence on the thermal management of the tank and the thermal management plays the limiting role in large-scale MH storage tanks, the experimental determination of the temperature-dependent effective thermal conductivity was of great importance

The previously mentioned experiential or also mathematically determined parameters were then incorporated into the simulations. At the beginning of the work, a simulation strategy was developed to check the experimentally determined parameters at an early stage and validate different relationships for the kinetic and thermodynamic behavior. The simulation strategy included the development of a simplified model of the tank in two dimensions, an extension of the complexity by the development of a 2D-axisymmetric model and the final development of an overly complex model in three spatial directions. The goal is always to simulate as complex as necessary but as simple as possible. As already described, the simulation started with the 2D model. Here all kinetic and thermodynamic relations of hydrogenation/dehydrogenation in the MH, were implemented. More complex was the implementation of the transport mechanisms of the hydrogen. Since the transport of hydrogen took place through porous media, such as the sinter filter and the hydride bed, as well as in free flow in the space between the pellet and the tank shell, the Brinkman equation had to be implemented. This was extensively simulated in the two-dimensional case and compared with the neglect of the free flow and the implementation of Darcy's law for the hydride bed. It turned out that there were only slight deviations in the change of porosity with time. Based on this finding, the calculation of the velocity field in the free flow with Brinkmann was dispensed with in the 2D axisymmetric model and in the 3D model, and only the Darcy law was implemented for the hydride bed. Only with this approach was it possible to calculate the simulation for the more complex models at all. For the convective heat transfer in the gaseous hydrogen between pellet and tank shell, the values of the velocity field were then taken from the 2D model. In order to be able to represent the coolant transport, which runs in the z-direction, in the 2D model, which is designed in the x-y-direction, a value was calculated for the convective heat transfer as a function of the coolant velocity. In order to verify the reliability of the obtained models, the simulated results were compared with the experimental data from the HyCARE tank. This was done for both absorption and desorption. It was found that for the 2D model as well as for the 2D axisymmetric model the behavior of the real tank could be mimicked in quite well agreement. In part, the absorption and desorption are somewhat faster than in the real tank, but the curve shows that in principle peak temperatures are reached at the same time and thus the simulation behaves very similarly to the real tank. Parameter and geometry optimizations were carried out. The goal was to find optimal parameter ranges that could represent notable

improvements and work out any limitations of the tank. For the 2D model, parameter variations of the temperature and the velocity of the coolant and the operating pressure were carried out. It turned out that the change of the coolant temperature reflects a linear behavior and that no limitations can be found in the selected temperature range. The choice of the temperature is therefore primarily dependent on what can be provided well. With the variation of the pressure, improvements could be shown for the absorption. For example, increasing the pressure from 30 bar to 35 bar had a strong effect on the amount of hydrogen that could be absorbed in 60 minutes. During desorption, it was found that the reaction came to a standstill when the pressure exceeded 7 bar. Larger effects were found with the variation of the coolant velocity. For both, absorption and desorption, it was found that increasing the coolant velocity from the experimentally used velocity of 0.3 m/s to a value of 2-4 m/s had an extremely high effect. However, with a further increase of the velocity, significantly smaller improvement of the reaction rate was observed. When the velocity was increased from 10 m/s to 15 m/s, hardly any improvement was observed. Geometry optimization was performed for the 2D axisymmetric model. The size of the pellets was varied. In the test set-up, 24 pellets are installed. For geometry optimization, different number of pellets keeping the same material mass was simulated. Changing the number of pellets, affects the surface area available for the hydrogen interaction. Therefore, considering the 24 pellets install in the experimental set up, simulations were carried out with 6 and 48 pellets. Thus, in the simulation considering 6 pellets, clearly showed how the increase in the heat exchange surface of the pellets affected the thermal properties of the tank. The reaction with 6 pellets reached higher peak temperatures but was only slightly slower than the reaction with 24 pellets. The difference between 24 pellets and 48 pellets was notable. Here, a similar difference in peak temperatures was seen, but the reaction was significantly faster

5.2 Prospect

The outlook for subsequent work can be viewed in a differentiated manner. On the one hand, further work can be done on the experimentally determined material behavior. On the other hand, the simulations and their results can also be worked on.

For the experimental part, further measurements for the effective thermal conductivity should be carried out to cover an even broader temperature spectrum and obtain statistical evaluations. Also, the number of charge and discharge cycles should be considered in a more detailed representation of the effective thermal conductivity. For the kinetic parameters, further measurements could be carried out to find a statistical average and take into account the pellet material with the binder. This also applies to thermodynamic equations for the enthalpy of reaction and entropy. Also, an equation for equilibrium pressure could still be determined from the PCI's. In this work, a formal was used which is also suitable for TiFeMn alloys and is already in good agreement with the PCI's, but it is an equation which was developed for the powder form.

Further efforts can be spent on extending the scope of the already existing parameter variation or varying new parameters for the simulation. This could be, for example, the diameter of the cooling tubes. Up to now, the parameter variation was always performed with only one variable parameter while the other parameters were fixed. Further work could deal with keeping several parameters variable to determine, for example, whether the varied results of the coolant temperature are also pressure dependent. A sensitivity analysis can also be performed to check which parameter is ultimately decisive for the reaction process. Optimization algorithms can also be used to discover optimal geometries or topologies, for example. Furthermore, work can be done on the 3D model to improve the geometrical representation and the mesh and develop a strategy to compute the Brinkman equation combined with a cluster computer. Finally, and this is probably the most extensive scope, elaborated parameter variations and optimizations can also be carried out for the geometry on the real HyCARE tank. This can then be compared with the simulated results and any necessary adjustments to the simulation can be made. In the end, the results of this work can be used and extended in many ways.

It is possible to develop applications (APPS) from existing COMSOL simulation in a relatively simple way. In a mobile and in a stationary case of a MH storage tank, an APP based on these results can provide various interesting information for the operation. For example, if a specific ambient temperature is available and the cooling system's temperature is known, this piece of information can be given on how quickly the MH storage tank can be loaded or unloaded. Also, statements about the capacity to be reached can be made relatively quickly.

Another example, especially in relation to the results of this work, would be that the temperature of the coolant is not easily changeable or is predetermined by the fuel cell. However, a certain capacity is to be absorbed or released within a certain time. Thus, a coolant pump with a variable flow rate based on the calculations of this work can fulfill the criteria mentioned above

6 References

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Appendix

A Modeling Parameter

The following basic parameters were used for the simulation. Equations for the kinetic and thermodynamic behavior can be found in the Results and Discussion chapter. A large part of the values is based on the values used for the operation of the real tank in the laboratory. Values for the material behavior that were not experimentally determined in this work have been taken from [13].

Absorption

Name	Value	Description
rho_AB2o	6471 [kg/m ³]	Crystalline density of AB2 -
Rho_AB2Ho	5460 [kg/m ³]	Crystalline density of the hydride
Ea	25.8 [kJ/mol]	Activation Energy
A	95 [1/s]	Frequency Factor
T0	25 [degC]	Initial Temperature
T0_Cooling	50 [degC]	Coolant temperature
P_max	30 [bar]	Operative Pressure
P_0	2.75 [bar]	Initial Pressure
Delta_s	-96.8 [J/mol*K]	Average Entropy
t_min	136 [min]	Time required to achieved p_max in the system
p_inlet	$(t < t_{min}) * ((p_{max} - p_0) / t_{min}) * t + p_0) + (t > t_{min}) * p_{max}$	Hydrogen inlet pressure, increasing from p_0 to p_max in a total time of t_min

Desorption

Name	Value	Description
rho_AB2o	6471 [kg/m ³]	Crystalline density of AB2 -
Rho_AB2Ho	5460 [kg/m ³]	Crystalline density of the hydride
Ea	12.8 [kJ/mol]	Activation Energy
A	122.4[1/s]	Frequency Factor

T0	50 [degC]	Initial Temperature
T0_Cooling	50 [degC]	Coolant temperature
P_max	2.75 [bar]	Operative Pressure
P_0	30 [bar]	Initial Pressure
Delta_s	-96.8 [J/mol*K]	Average Entropy
p_outlet 1	$(t < t1) * ((10.12219 + 22.11168 * 0.98886^{(t/te)}) * 1$ [bar]	Hydrogen outlet pressure
p_outlet 2	$(t > t1) * (t < t2) * (p_max / (1$ [bar]) + 7.13541 * 0.99886^{(t/te)}) * 1 [bar]	
p_outlet 3	$(t > t2) * p_max$	
t1	300 [s]	Time to reach first function
t2	8583 [s]	Time to reach second function

Fig A1

B Curve fitting of the kinetic behavior (Gas-solid)

This approach to the kinetic behavior of the TiFeMn alloy was used at the beginning of the work to obtain initial values for the kinetic behavior. In the further course of the work, kinetic parameters based on the pelletized hydride material were generated and used for the simulation.

These parameter estimations and curve fittings, which can be found below, were created, and provided by *Dr. Julián Puszkiet*.

Absorption

Fig. A2-A7

Desorption

Absorption

Desorption

Applying the gas-solid model for 4D-diffusion as used in the FEM simulation

$$g(\alpha) = kt \quad 1 - (2/3)\alpha - (1 - \alpha)^{2/3} = kt$$

↑ Model ↑ Slope

Fitting done from 0.1 to 0.8 of the fraction

Final Fitting

Absorption

k(T,P)	0.02038 1/s
F(P)	$(P - P_{eq}) / P_{eq}$
P	25bar
P _{eq} (55 °C)	10.09bar
F(P)	1.477701
K(T)	$A \cdot \text{EXP}[-E_a / R_g \cdot T]$
E _a	-23800J/mol H ₂
T	328K
R _g	8.31J/ K*mol
A	1.26E+02 1/s

Desorption

k(T,P)	0.00181/s
F(P)	$(P_{eq} - P) / P_{eq}$
P	1bar
P _{eq} (55 °C)	5.87var
F(P)	0.829642
K(T)	$A \cdot \text{EXP}[-E_a / R_g \cdot T]$
E _a	-19870J/mol H ₂
T	328K
R _g	8.31J/ K*mol
A	2.64 1/s

C Fitting of effective thermal conductivity and example calculation

Example Calculation for effective thermal conductivity

T= 50 °C

Absorption

Equation for the calculation of the effective thermal conductivity is shown below.

$$k_{eff} == \frac{q * rho}{4 * m}$$

Two further fittings for q and m were made.

Fig. A8

$$T - T_c = m * r^2$$

$$m = -0,23187 \frac{K}{mm^2} \text{ (from fitting)}$$

Fig. A9

$$q = \text{rate}_{H_2} * \Delta H$$

The slope of 0.01214 represents the amount of hydrogen which is absorbed in wt%/s. For the calculation of q it is convert to mol/kg*s.

$$\text{rate}_{H_2} = 0.061 \text{ mol/kg*s}$$

$$k_{eff_{50^\circ C}} = 9.397 \text{ W/mK}$$

Absorption

Desorption

Absorption

Fig. A11-A14

Desorption

E COMSOL graphs for parametric variations

Absorption:

Fig. A12-A14

Desorption

Fig. A15-A17

F List of primary data

Figure	Source	Primary Data Location: WTS(\rszfs0020)(V:) Primary data/2021_Masterarbeit_Patrick_Kloss/
Fig. 10	Keff Determination	/Keff primary data
Fig. 11	HyCARE_1001969_Te stmodul	/Tank_info
Fig. 12	3d_sampleholder_Abs. mph	/Simulations/3D/Sample Holder
Fig. 13	3d_sampleholder_Abs. mph	/Simulations/3D/Sample Holder
Fig. 14	2D-model-xy_Abs.	/Simulations/2D/Absorption
Fig. 15	2D-model-xy_Abs.	/Simulations/2D/Absorption
Fig. 16	2D-model-xy_Abs.	/Simulations/2D/Absorption
Fig. 17	3D_Tank_2D_axisymet ric_Darcy_Abs	/Simulations/2D-Axisymmetric/Absorption
Fig. 18	3D_Tank_2D_axisymet ric_Darcy_Abs	/Simulations/2D-Axisymmetric/Absorption
Fig. 19	3D_Tank_2D_axisymet ric_Darcy_Abs	/Simulations/2D-Axisymmetric/Absorption
Fig. 20	Model 3D- HyCARE_des_Hydroge nation	/Simulations/3D
Fig. 21	Model 3D- HyCARE_des_Hydroge nation	/Simulations/3D
Fig. 22	3d_sampleholder_Abs. mph	/Simulations/3D/Sample Holder
Fig. 23	3d_sampleholder_Des. mph	/Simulations/3D/Sample Holder
Fig. 25	Keff Determination	/Keff primary data
Fig. 26	Keff Determination	/Keff primary data
Fig. 27	Keff Determination	/Keff primary data
Fig. 29	2D-model-xy_Abs.	/Simulations/2D/Absorption
Fig. 33	2D-model-xy_Des.	/Simulations/2D/Desorption
Fig. 34	2D-model-xy_Abs.	/Simulations/2D/Absorption
Fig. 35	2D-model-xy_Abs.	/Simulations/2D/Absorption
Fig. 36	Parameter variations	/Parameter Variations
Fig. 37	Parameter variations	/Parameter Variations
Fig. 38	Parameter variations	/Parameter Variations
Fig. 39	2D-model-xy_Des.	/Simulations/2D/Desorption
Fig. 40	2D-model-xy_Des.	/Simulations/2D/Desorption
Fig. 41	Parameter variations	/Parameter Variations
Fig. 42	Parameter variations	/Parameter Variations

Fig. 43	Parameter variations	/Parameter Variations
Fig. 44	3D_Tank_2D_axisymet ric_Darcy_Abs	/Simulations/2D-Axisymmetric/Absorption
Fig. 45	3D_Tank_2D_axisymet ric_Darcy_Abs	/Simulations/2D-Axisymmetric/Absorption
Fig. 46	3D_Tank_2D_axisymet ric_Darcy_Abs_Pellet_ optimization	/Simulations/2D-Axisymmetric/Absorption
Fig. 47	3D_Tank_2D_axisymet ric_Darcy_Abs_Pellet_ optimization	/Simulations/2D-Axisymmetric/Absorption
Fig. 48	3D_Tank_2D_axisymet ric_Darcy_Des	/Simulations/2D-Axisymmetric/Desorption
Fig. 49	3D_Tank_2D_axisymet ric_Darcy_Des	/Simulations/2D-Axisymmetric/Desorption
Fig. 50	3D_Tank_2D_axisymet ric_Darcy_Des	/Simulations/2D-Axisymmetric/Desorption
Fig. 51	3D_Tank_2D_axisymet ric_Darcy_Des	/Simulations/2D-Axisymmetric/Desorption
Fig. 52	Model 3D- HyCARE_des_Hydroge nation	/Simulations/3D
Fig. 53	Model 3D- HyCARE_des_Hydroge nation	/Simulations/3D
Fig. A1	2D-model-xy_Des.	/Simulations/2D/Desorption
Fig. A2-A7	Fitting-Model- Hydrogenation-FeTiMn/ Fitting-Model- Dehydrogenation	/Julián_solid_gas_model
Fig. A8	Keff determination	/Keff primary data
Fig. A9	Keff determination	/Keff primary data
Fig. A10	HyCARE_WP03_20200 331_GKN_ASIS- DH_primary data_PCl	/DeltaH,DeltaS data
Fig. A11- A11	VH-determination	/DeltaH,DeltaS data
Fig. A12	2D- model_xy_Abs._Coolin g_Temp	/Simulations/2D/Absorption
Fig. A13	2D- model_xy_Abs._sweep _p_max	/Simulations/2D/Absorption

Fig. A14	2D- model_xy_Abs._sweep _velocity_cooling	/Simulations/2D/Absorption
Fig. A15	2D- model_xy_Des._param etric_sweep_Temp.	/Simulations/2D/Desorption
Fig. A16	2D- model_xy_Des._param etric_sweep_p_max	/Simulations/2D/Desorption
Fig. A17	2D- model_xy_Des._param etric_sweep_velocity	/Simulations/2D/Desorption
